

TRADITIONAL MEDICINE IN THE KHIV KHANATE

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Xiva xonligida XIX – XX asr boshlarida an’anaviy tibbiyotning shakllanishi, rivojlanish bosqichlari, tabiblar faoliyati hamda davolash amaliyotlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda mahalliy yozma manbalar, tibbiy qo’lyozmalar, xorijiy sayyohlar va rus sharqshunoslarining ma’lumotlari qiyosiy yondashuv asosida o’rganiladi. Shuningdek, g’arb tibbiyotining kirib kelishi natijasida yuzaga kelgan o’zgarishlar ham yoritiladi.

Kalit so’zlar: Xiva xonligi, an’anaviy tibbiyot, tabiblar, Ibn Sino, Abulg’ozi Bahodirxon, Nasriddin Hazorasbiy, hijoma, xalq tabobati.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются формирование, этапы развития традиционной медицины в Хивинском ханстве в XIX – начале XX века, а также деятельность табибов и лечебная практика. В исследовании на основе сравнительного подхода изучаются местные письменные источники, медицинские рукописи, а также сведения зарубежных путешественников и российских востоковедов. Кроме того, рассматриваются изменения, произошедшие под влиянием проникновения западной медицины.

Ключевые слова: Хивинское ханство, традиционная медицина, табибы, Ибн Сина, Абулгази Бахадурхан, Насриддин Хазарасбий, хиджама (кровопускание), народная медицина.

Anotation: This article analyzes the formation and development stages of traditional medicine in the Khiva Khanate during the 19th and early 20th centuries, as well as the activities of traditional healers (tabibs) and medical practices. The study employs a comparative approach based on local written sources, medical manuscripts, accounts of foreign travelers, and works of Russian orientalists. It also examines the social and medical transformations that occurred as a result of the introduction of Western medicine into the region.

Keywords: Khiva Khanate, traditional medicine, tabibs (healers), Ibn Sina, Abulgazi Bahadur Khan, Nasriddin Hazorasbiy, hijama (cupping), folk medicine.

Traditional medicine in the Khiva Khanate was formed over centuries of historical processes and is manifested as a complex and multi-layered system that has gone through its own development path¹. In the formation of this system, the experiences of folk medicine, Eastern scientific traditions, written medical heritage, and religious and mystical views were combined and developed in a complementary manner. As a result, medicine in the Khiva Khanate was formed not only as a means of treating diseases, but also as an important area closely related to the cultural, spiritual and social life of society.

In particular, by the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, this medical system became more complex and significantly developed in terms of its internal structure and practical directions². During this period, the activities of doctors expanded, methods of treating diseases diversified, and the use of medicinal plants and natural remedies was further improved. At the same time, religious and practical treatment methods also continued to retain their importance in the life of society. This indicates that the medicine of the Khiva Khanate existed as a multi-component and integrated system.

The development of medicine during this period was not limited only to practical needs, but was also associated with the processes of relying on scientific heritage, creating written sources,

¹ Qayumov A. Xiva xonligida tibbiyot tarixi. – Toshkent: Fan, 1998. – B. 45–52.

² To’rayev H. Xiva xonligining madaniy hayoti (XIX asr oxiri – XX asr boshi). – Buxoro, 2011. – B. 78–84.

and systematizing knowledge passed down from generation to generation. Therefore, by studying the history of medicine of the Khiva Khanate, one can not only obtain information about treatment practices and diseases, but also draw important conclusions about the level of scientific thinking of that time.

A deep analysis of the state of medicine during this period, on the one hand, allows us to determine the level of development of the healthcare system, and on the other hand, sheds light on social aspects such as the daily lifestyle of the population, sanitary and hygienic culture, nutrition and living conditions, as well as their attitude to diseases. In addition, views in the field of medicine through which it is possible to understand the religious beliefs, traditions and spiritual values of the society.

From this point of view, the history of medicine of the Khiva Khanate is not only a part of medical science, but also one of the important scientific directions where history, ethnography, cultural studies and social sciences intersect in a broad sense. By studying it, an opportunity is created to understand the internal structure of the past society, the relationship between man and society, and the processes of cultural development more deeply.

The main scientific supporting sources in the study of the history of medicine of the Khiva Khanate in the period up to 1873 are of different nature, and they are divided into several directions according to their content and origin. In general, a comparative analysis of local and foreign sources is of great importance in order to form a complete picture of the medical system of this period. Because both types of sources provide complementary information, they also have their own limitations and subjective aspects.

Information about the medicine of the Khiva Khanate is mainly reflected in two large groups of sources: the first is medical and historical works and manuscripts created in the local environment, and the second is travelogues and memoirs written by foreign tourists, ambassadors and military observers. Through these sources, we get a certain idea of the types of diseases, methods of treatment, the activities of doctors and practical aspects of folk medicine of that time. Local sources, especially works and historical manuscripts created by doctors, are the most important scientific basis for illuminating the system of internal medical knowledge, theoretical views and practical experiences of the Khiva Khanate. These sources often provide detailed information about the causes of diseases, their symptoms, treatment methods and medicinal products. They also cover the transmission of medical knowledge from generation to generation, the traditions of the master-disciple relationship and the role of the medical profession in society. However, a significant drawback of these sources is that they often lack systematic scientific classification and, in some cases, are presented in the form of short and fragmentary information. Therefore, their analysis requires a historical-comparative and comprehensive approach. Foreign sources, on the other hand, were formed mainly on the basis of observations of Russian diplomats, military officers and European tourists, and they cover medical life in the Khiva Khanate from an external point of view. These sources describe diseases common among the population, the activities of doctors, specific aspects of treatment methods, as well as rituals and practices related to folk medicine. At the same time, some subjective approaches are also observed in such sources due to the personal views of the authors, cultural differences and incomplete understanding of local conditions. This further increases the need for their critical scientific analysis.

In the study of the history of Khiva medicine, the scientific heritage of the East, in particular the teachings of Abu Ali Ibn Sina, occupies a special place. Ibn Sina's views on medicine had a strong influence not only on the entire Islamic world, but also on the activities of doctors in Central Asia, including the Khiva Khanate. His classification of diseases, diagnostic methods

and treatment principles were widely used in the practice of local doctors and were continued in the medical works of the next generation³.

In this regard, the medicine of the Khiva Khanate was formed as a complex system that developed on the basis of, on the one hand, the experience and practical knowledge of the local people, and on the other hand, the great scientific traditions of the East⁴. This indicates that the medical field had a consistent scientific tradition in its time and that it developed continuously.

In the history of the Khiva Khanate, Abulgozi Bakhodir Khan occupies a special place not only as a political figure and statesman, but also as a scientist who made a significant contribution to the development of science, in particular, to the fields of history and medicine. His scientific heritage is one of the important stages in the formation of the cultural and scientific thought of Central Asia, and the works he created were of great importance as a scientific source both in his time and in subsequent periods.

Abulgozi Bakhodir Khan's work "Manofi' al-inson" ("Useful Measures for Man") is one of the most important written monuments of the medical thought of the Khiva Khanate. This work is distinguished by its focus on systematization of medical knowledge, generalization of diseases and methods of their treatment. In the work, the author tried to summarize the medical knowledge of his time and describe them on the basis of practical experience and observations.

This work describes in detail more than 100 types of diseases, their causes, clinical symptoms and methods of treatment⁵. The description of diseases is distinguished not by their classification and attempt to explain them on the basis of a specific system, but by the fact that medical knowledge at that time was scientific to a certain extent and developed based on practical experience.

The work also contains information on a number of important areas of medicine. In particular, the issues of surgical operations, children's diseases (pediatrics), skin diseases (dermatology), diseases of the eyes and organs of vision (ophthalmology), and the use of medicinal substances (pharmacology) are widely covered. This indicates that medicine in the Khiva Khanate was not limited to general medical practice, but also formed some specialized areas.

In this work of Abulgozi Bakhodir Khan, approaches based on natural remedies, herbal medicines, and traditional medicine methods play a priority role in the treatment of diseases. This confirms the inextricable connection of Khiva medicine with the traditional medical schools of the East, in particular, the heritage of Ibn Sina.

In general, the work "Manofi' al-inson" is an important scientific source indicating the development of the medical field in the Khiva Khanate in a certain degree of systematization and specialization. Through this work, it can be seen that medicine at that time was not just a practical profession, but a system of knowledge with a scientific basis. This once again confirms the important place that medicine played in the scientific and cultural life of the Khiva Khanate.

³ Karimov U.I. Abu Ali ibn Sino va uning tibbiy merosi. – Toshkent: Fan, 1980. – B. 42–48.

⁴ Sodiqov A. "O'zbekistonda tibbiyot tarixi", T.: 1991, 56-bet

⁵ Abulg'ozzi Bahodirxon. Manofi' al-inson (Inson uchun foydali tadbirlar). Nashrga tayyorlovchilar: B. Abduhalimov, H. Hikmatullayev. – Toshkent: Fan, 1994. – B. 5–12.

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